

Interview Guiding Question

Introduction, Ice-Breaker	Could you talk a bit about your current position and your background?
Policy/Strategic Fit	How do you see the role of AI and robotics in future education systems? What national/regional strategies exist for digital education?
Current Landscape	What are the most common technological resources used in classrooms today? Where do you see the biggest gaps in teacher preparedness for using robotics in classrooms?
Barriers, Enablers	What financial, logistical, or regulatory obstacles hinder the adoption of using robotics platforms in education? Are there existing funding mechanisms that could be leveraged to support schools?
Curriculum Alignment	How could a modular robotics curriculum be mapped onto national standards/curricula (e.g., digital basic education, science, ICT, vocational pathways)?
Equality, Inclusion	Which groups (by geography, socioeconomic status, gender, special-needs) are most at risk of being left out of emerging AI/robotics education? What measures would you recommend to guarantee equitable access?
Feedback on ARAISE	What are your first impressions of the ARAISE “open-source platform + lending system” concept? Which aspects would you modify to better fit your national context?
Closure	Do you have any further comments or suggestions?